

Smoothing of linear partial differential equation in view of Green's function

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Abstract:

for the numerical data having more data points, for sake of ease, the method of cubic spline interpolation is considered optimal. A polynomial of higher degree can be written as the product of linear and quadratic polynomials in a complex plane by fundamental theorem of algebra. So, a linear 2nd order partial differential equation can be seen as two 2nd order ordinary differential equations by fixing each argument of one variable as constant and solve the equation for the 2nd variable. So, to solve a 2nd order differential equation that has two implicit variables t and s , one can apply a Green's function and solve it. The action is suitable to both the explicit variables x and y , equating the solutions of both the differential equations at each case, we can get the generalization that represents the required integral surface.

Key words: Linear partial differential operator, adjoint differential operator, boundary conditions, closed region, enclosing curve, normal, surface integral, linearly independent solutions

Introduction:

If $z = f(x(t_1), y(t_2))$ is a smooth integral surface in the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 obtained from the partial differential equation $L(z) = f(x, y)$ that can again be split as $L_1(z) = f_1(x, y)$ and $L_2(z) = f_2(x, y)$ where $L_1: [a, b] \rightarrow [c, d]$ by $L_1(z_1) = L(\frac{\partial z}{\partial x})$, $L_2: [e, f] \rightarrow [c, d]$ by $L_2(z_2) = L(\frac{\partial z}{\partial y})$,

Along OX, OX', OY, OY' axes, the surface is not smooth; however the surface is closed and continuous. So, while solving a partial differential equation to find $\pi = P(\theta, \vartheta)$ at the arbitrary point P , so, the partial differential equation can be factorized to apply Green's function independent for $L_1(z_1) = h_1(x)$ and $L_2(z_2) = h_2(y)$. While dealing with the boundary value problems, z_1 & z_2 are periodic functions. Extending this discussion to the closed surfaces, it can be taken as $z_1(c) = z_1(d)$ and $z_2(c) = z_2(d)$ where c, d are finite real numbers. 1.0

The linear partial differential equation

$$\chi_1(x, y) \frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial x \partial y} + \chi_2(x) \frac{\partial z}{\partial x} + \chi_3(y) \frac{\partial z}{\partial y} + \chi_4(x, y) z = 0 \quad \dots\dots 1.1$$

can be compressed when each of the cases of y are considered as constants as the Sturm – Liouville problem as

$$(p_1 z_1')' + q_1 z_1 + \lambda_1 r_1 z_1 = 0 \text{ where } z_1 = z_1(x(t_1)), c \leq t_1 \leq d, z_1 = z(x) \quad \dots\dots 1.2$$

Similarly, (1.1) can otherwise be compressed as

$$(p_2 z_2')' + q_2 z_2 + \lambda_2 r_2 z_2 = 0 \text{ where } z_2 = z_2(y(t_2)), c \leq t_2 \leq d, z_2 = z(y) \quad \dots\dots 1.3$$

(1.2) can be expressed in the linear form $L_1(z_1(t_1)) = h_1(x(t_1))$ where

$$L_1(z_1(t_1)) = (p_1 z_1')' + q_1 z_1 \text{ and } h_1(x(t_1)) = \lambda_1 r_1 z_1 \quad \dots\dots 1.4$$

(1.3) is written in the form $L_2(z_2(t_2)) = h_2(y(t_2))$ where $L_2(z_2(t_2)) = (p_2 z_2')' + q_2 z_2$ and

$$h_2(y(t_2)) = \lambda_2 r_2 z_2 \quad \dots\dots 1.5$$

Observe that (1.4) and (1.5) are the linear differential equations with same dependent variable and the boundary conditions are $c \leq t_1, t_2 \leq d$ and have to satisfy

$$\alpha_1 z_1(c) + \beta_1 z_{1x}(c) = 0; \quad \dots\dots 1.6.1$$

$$\alpha_1 z_1(d) + \beta_1 z_{1x}(d) = 0 \quad \dots\dots 1.6.2$$

$$\alpha_2 z_2(c) + \beta_2 z_{2y}(c) = 0 \quad \dots\dots 1.7.1$$

$$\alpha_2 z_2(d) + \beta_2 z_{2y}(d) = 0 \quad \dots\dots 1.7.2$$

Note that $z_{1x} = \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial x}$ and $z_{2y} = \frac{\partial z_2}{\partial y}$.

$$z_1(c) = z_1(d) \text{ and } z_2(c) = z_2(d) \quad \dots\dots 1.7.3$$

Definition: for each fixed value of y , a function $\Gamma_1(t_1, s)$ defined on $[a, b] \times [c, d]$ called the Green's function for $L_1(z_1) = 0$ if the following conditions are satisfied.

- i. For any s , $\Gamma_1(t_1, s) = \Gamma_{11}(t_1, s)$ when $t_1 < s$ and $\Gamma_1(t_1, s) = \Gamma_{12}(t_1, s)$ when $t_1 > s$
- ii. Γ_{11} satisfies (1.6.1) at $t_1 = c$, $L_1(\Gamma_{11}) = 0$ for $t_1 < s$
- iii. Γ_{12} satisfies (1.6.2) at $t_1 = d$, $L_1(\Gamma_{12}) = 0$ for $t_1 > s$
- iv. The function Γ_1 is continuous at $t_1 = s$
- v. The partial derivative of Γ_1 with respect to t_1 has a jump discontinuity at $t_1 = s$ and

$$\left. \frac{\partial \Gamma_{12}}{\partial t_1} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{11}}{\partial t_1} \right|_{t_1=s} = \frac{-1}{p_1(s)} \dots\dots 1.74$$

Definition: for each fixed value of x , a function $\Gamma_2(t_2, s)$ defined on $[e, f] \times [c, d]$ called the Green's function for $L_2(z_2) = 0$ if the following conditions are satisfied.

- i. For any s , $\Gamma_2(t_2, s) = \Gamma_{21}(t_2, s)$ when $t_2 < s$ and $\Gamma_2(t_2, s) = \Gamma_{22}(t_2, s)$ when $t_2 > s$
- ii. Γ_{21} satisfies (1.7.1) at $t_2 = c$, $L_2(\Gamma_{21}) = 0$ for $t_2 < s$
- iii. Γ_{22} satisfies (1.7.2) at $t_2 = d$, $L_2(\Gamma_{22}) = 0$ for $t_2 > s$
- iv. The function Γ_2 is continuous at $t_2 = s$
- v. The partial derivative of Γ_2 with respect to t_2 has a jump discontinuity at $t_2 = s$ and

$$\left. \frac{\partial \Gamma_{22}}{\partial t_2} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{21}}{\partial t_2} \right|_{t_2=s} = \frac{-1}{p_2(s)} \dots\dots 1.75$$

Observe that when $p_1(s) = p_2(s)$, from (1.1), also, that Γ_{11} and Γ_{12} are linearly independent continuous functions for each fixed value of Γ_{21} or Γ_{22} and vice versa.

$$\Gamma_1 \left\{ \frac{\partial \Gamma_{22}}{\partial t_2} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{21}}{\partial t_2} \right\} - \Gamma_2 \left\{ \frac{\partial \Gamma_{12}}{\partial t_1} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{11}}{\partial t_1} \right\} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ \chi_2 \Gamma_1 \Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1 \frac{\partial \Gamma_2}{\partial t_2} \right\} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left\{ \chi_1 \Gamma_1 \Gamma_2 + \Gamma_2 \frac{\partial \Gamma_1}{\partial t_1} \right\} \text{ by Green's theorem at the arbitrary point } P(\theta, \vartheta) \text{ on the surface } z = f(x, y) \dots\dots 1.76$$

To evaluate z at $P(\theta, \vartheta)$, observe that Γ_1 and Γ_2 are adjoint operators to each other. The surface z is spanned by two independent vectors or solutions with respect to $x(t_1)$ and two independent vectors with respect to (t_2) .

In view of definition (1.74), let $G(t_1, s) = \begin{cases} c_1 z_{11}, & t_1 \leq s \\ c_2 z_{12}, & t_1 \geq s \end{cases}$ where the choice of c_1 and c_2 will satisfy $c_2 z_{11} - c_1 z_{12} = 0$ and $c_1 z'_{12} - c_2 z'_{11} = 0 \dots\dots 1.77$

Also, in view of (1.75), $G(t_2, s) = \begin{cases} d_1 z_{21}, & t_2 \leq s \\ d_2 z_{22}, & t_2 \geq s \end{cases}$ with $d_2 z_{21} - d_1 z_{22} = 0$ and $d_1 z'_{22} - d_2 z'_{21} = 0 \dots\dots 1.78$

The choice of c_1, c_2 can be to satisfy (1.74) and (1.77) as $c_1 z_{12}(s) - c_2 z_{11}(s) = 0$ and $c_1 z'_{12}(s) - c_2 z'_{11}(s) = \frac{-1}{p_1(s)} \dots\dots 1.79$

Also, the choice of d_1, d_2 can satisfy (1.75) and (1.78) as $d_1 z_{22}(s) - d_2 z_{21}(s) = 0$ and $d_1 z'_{12}(s) - d_2 z'_{11}(s) = \frac{-1}{p_2(s)} \dots\dots 1.80$

(1.79) and (1.80) satisfy $L_1(z_1) = 0$ and $L_2(z_2) = 0$ respectively.

Observe that $z_{11}(p_1 z'_{12})' - z_{12}(p_1 z'_{11})' = \frac{d}{dt_1} \{ p_1 (z_{11} z'_{12} - z_{12} z'_{11}) \} = 0$ from the homogeneity of the above equation.

From this, $p_1(z_{11} z'_{12} - z_{12} z'_{11}) = \xi_1$ a nonzero constant for every $c \leq t_1 \leq d$

In other words, $(z_{11} z'_{12} - z_{12} z'_{11}) = \frac{\xi_1}{p_1}$

Solving (1.77) and this, it follows $c_1 = \frac{-z_{21}(s)}{\xi_1}$ and $c_2 = \frac{-z_{22}(s)}{\xi_1}$

$$\text{This helps us to draw } \Gamma_1(t_1, s) = \begin{cases} -z_{11}(t_1)z_{12}(s)/\xi_1, & t_1 \leq s \\ -z_{12}(t_1)z_{11}(s)/\xi_1, & s \leq t_1 \end{cases} \quad \dots\dots 1.81$$

A similar argument by keeping x a constant, for different t_2 values of y in (1.75), (1.78) and (1.80) give $\Gamma_2(t_2, s) = \begin{cases} -z_{21}(t_2)z_{22}(s)/\xi_2, & t_2 \leq s \\ -z_{22}(t_2)z_{21}(s)/\xi_2, & s \leq t_2 \end{cases} \quad \dots\dots 1.82$

If $z = f(x, y)$ is a bounded region \mathfrak{N} enclosed by a curve \mathfrak{S} satisfying (1.0), Γ_{11}, Γ_{12} and Γ_{12}, Γ_{22} are respectively pairwise mutually adjoint operators, which by Green's theorem follow

$$\iint_{\mathfrak{N}} (\Gamma_{12}L_1\Gamma_{11} - \Gamma_{11}L_2\Gamma_{12})d\theta d\vartheta = \int (\chi_2\Gamma_{11}\Gamma_{12} - \Gamma_{12}\frac{\partial\Gamma_{11}}{\partial\vartheta})d\vartheta - (\chi_3\Gamma_{11}\Gamma_{12} - \Gamma_{11}\frac{\partial\Gamma_{12}}{\partial\theta})d\theta \quad \dots\dots 1.83$$

$$\iint_{\mathfrak{N}} (\Gamma_{21}L_1\Gamma_{22} - \Gamma_{22}L_2\Gamma_{21})d\theta d\vartheta = \int (\chi_2\Gamma_{21}\Gamma_{22} - \Gamma_{21}\frac{\partial\Gamma_{22}}{\partial\vartheta})d\vartheta - (\chi_3\Gamma_{21}\Gamma_{22} - \Gamma_{22}\frac{\partial\Gamma_{21}}{\partial\theta})d\theta \quad \dots\dots 1.84$$

If \vec{u} is the normal vector to the surface $z = f(x, y)$ at $P(\theta, \vartheta)$, then (1.83) can also be observed as $\int (\chi_2\Gamma_{11}\Gamma_{12} - \Gamma_{12}\frac{\partial\Gamma_{11}}{\partial\vartheta}) \cos(\vec{u}, \theta) d\mathfrak{N} + (\chi_3\Gamma_{11}\Gamma_{12} - \Gamma_{11}\frac{\partial\Gamma_{12}}{\partial\theta}) \cos(\vec{u}, \vartheta) d\mathfrak{N}_{\mathfrak{S}}$

In view of Morera's theorem and homotopic version of Cauchy's theorem, taking the function $\Gamma_1(t_1, s)$ is

$$\chi_2\Gamma_{12} - \frac{\partial\Gamma_{12}}{\partial\vartheta} = 0 \text{ along } \vartheta = z_{12} \quad \dots\dots 1.91$$

$$\chi_3\Gamma_{12} - \frac{\partial\Gamma_{12}}{\partial\theta} = 0 \text{ along } \theta = z_{11} \quad \dots\dots 1.92$$

$$\Gamma_{12} = 1 \text{ along } \vartheta = z_{12} \text{ and } \theta = z_{11} \quad \dots\dots 1.93$$

The mutual adjoint operators Γ_{11} and Γ_{12} shows that z_{12} is the Green's function that helps to give

$$[z]_P = \frac{1}{2} \{ [\Gamma_{11}\Gamma_{12}]_A + [\Gamma_{11}\Gamma_{12}]_B \} - \int_{AB} \Gamma_{11}\Gamma_{12} \{ \chi_2 d\vartheta - \chi_3 d\theta \} - \frac{1}{2} \int_{AB} \Gamma_{12} \left\{ \frac{\partial\Gamma_{11}}{\partial\vartheta} d\vartheta - \frac{\partial\Gamma_{11}}{\partial\theta} d\theta \right\} - \frac{1}{2} \int_{AB} \Gamma_{11} \left\{ \frac{\partial\Gamma_{12}}{\partial\vartheta} d\vartheta - \frac{\partial\Gamma_{12}}{\partial\theta} d\theta \right\} + \iint_{\mathfrak{N}} (\Gamma_{12} f) d\theta d\vartheta \quad \dots\dots 2.1$$

$$[z]_P = \frac{1}{2} \{ [\Gamma_{21}\Gamma_{22}]_A + [\Gamma_{21}\Gamma_{22}]_B \} - \int_{AB} \Gamma_{21}\Gamma_{22} \{ \chi_2 d\vartheta - \chi_3 d\theta \} - \frac{1}{2} \int_{AB} \Gamma_{22} \left\{ \frac{\partial\Gamma_{21}}{\partial\vartheta} d\vartheta - \frac{\partial\Gamma_{21}}{\partial\theta} d\theta \right\} - \frac{1}{2} \int_{AB} \Gamma_{21} \left\{ \frac{\partial\Gamma_{22}}{\partial\vartheta} d\vartheta - \frac{\partial\Gamma_{22}}{\partial\theta} d\theta \right\} + \iint_{\mathfrak{N}} (\Gamma_{22} f) d\theta d\vartheta \quad \dots\dots 2.2$$

The surface z is determined from the equations (2.1) = (2.2) where $z = f(x, y)$ represents a surface of a closed region \mathfrak{R} enclosed by a curve \mathfrak{J} and A, B are the points on the curve \mathfrak{J} joined by the lines from $P(\theta, \vartheta)$ parallel to $y = \vartheta$ and $x = \theta$ respectively.

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